

ANTHROPOCENTRISM IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK PHRASEOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Anthropocentrism has been taking the leading role in linguistics since 20th century. As the man has always been in the main role of the linguistics, they are also integral part of the language. Anthropocentric phraseology became important as the researchers started learning the phraseology by putting the man in the centre. In this article you will be informed about Anthropocentrism in English and Karakalpak phraseology especially somatic phraseological units in English and Karakalpak languages. This article includes some examples of English idioms which have equivalent in Karakalpak language.

Introduction

Anthropocentrism has become one of the most important directions at the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st centuries. The usage of anthropocentric principle or the principle of “the man in the language” (Benveniste, 1974) takes a special place in linguistics.

According to the principle of anthropocentrism, a person speaking the language can acquire the language in the process of using it as the language ‘has no other objectivity except for the one which is confirmed in the depth of subjectivity’ [Guillaume 1971], i.e. the language becomes subjective while being used.

The principle of ‘man in the language’ or anthropocentrism was discussed in the Russian phraseology long ago. I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay in his work ‘Phonology’ (1899) singled out anthropophonics as a science concerned with the sound of human speech. The above mentioned principle has a reflection in the works of N.D.Arutunova, A. Vezhbitskaya, U.D.Asparian. Researchers call this shift in interest toward a man ‘an anthropocentric shift’ in linguistics at the end of the 20th century. (Vorozhbitova 2003).

The research of phraseology on the principle of “man in the language” has brought a new development in the linguistics – anthropocentric phraseology.

Somatic idioms in Karakalpak and English

Somatic idioms are the idioms whose one of the constituents is a part of the body. There are some examples in Karakalpak language. Head which is one of the most essential part of the body, if it is used in idioms, it has a lot of different meanings in Karakalpak language. For example:

Bası birigiw- if we translate this idiom into English word by word, it is translated “to connect heads”. This idiom is used when people make a group.

Basına baxıt qonıw- “To take off happiness to one’s head”. It is used when someone is lucky or happy. Moreover, it is used if someone’s business is

Basına jetiw- “To reach someone’s head”. It is used when somebody dies because of someone’s fault.

Basın alıp ketiw- “To take out head”-to leave.

Bası pispew- Some people's heads are not riped-means that some people cannot agree or they often argue with each other.

Awzı ashıq- “Open mouth”. To be stupid.

Awzına qum quyıw- “To put sand into someone’s mouth”. To keep calm. It is used when somebody does not speak a word.

Awzına as salıw- “To put food into someone’s mouth”. It is used when someone’s children are grown-ups and they can supply the family.

Awız tiyiw- “To touch mouth”. This idiom is connected with the culture. When someone visits somebody’s house briefly, they will be given some bread. They should eat a piece of bread.

There are some English idioms which have the equivalents in Karakalpak language. For example:

To take the law into their own hands-Óz qolına alıw (to take action which should be taken by the police or the courts). This idiom in English means only about the police or the courts but in Karakalpak it is general.

Something is on the tip of somebody’s tongue- Tildiń ushında turıw(you know it but cannot quite remember it)

Get out of hand- Qoldan jiberiw(get out of control). In this idiom “hand” is used in the same way and there is no difference between the meaning in two languages.

Change hands- Qollı bolıw(been sold to a new owner). In karakalpak language, qollı bolıw means two different meaning. The first one is when something is stolen, and the second meaning is the same as in English.

Give a hand-Járdem qolın beriw(to help).

Stand on your own two feet- Ayaqqa turıw(to be independent). In English this means to be independent but in Karakalpak this idiom is used in a lot of different situations. For instance: when somebody has suffered from an illness, and now he/she is better, then we can use this idiom. When somebody has suffered from financial problems, and now everything is normal, in this situation the idiom can be used.

Conclusion

Since we have seen from these anthropocentric phraseology in both English and Karakalpak languages, there are some equivalents nevertheless, there are also some idioms which do not have any equivalents because of linguocultural peculiarities..

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